

New 30m Annual NDVI Time Series 2000-2023 from Mixed Landsat Images

Tools and dataset to support UNCCD 2026 reporting cycle in
40 Small Island Development States (SIDS)

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Introduction

Small Island Developing States (SIDS) depend heavily on the health and productivity of their land to sustain livelihoods, food security, and climate resilience. Land degradation, driven by pressures such as climate change, land use conversion, and extreme weather events, directly impacts agricultural productivity, freshwater resources, and the stability of coastal and terrestrial ecosystems. These vulnerabilities make the effective monitoring and management of land resources critical to safeguarding sustainable development in SIDS.

In recognition of these challenges, Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) Target 15.3 calls for countries to “strive to achieve a land degradation-neutral world” by 2030. Progress towards this target is tracked through SDG Indicator 15.3.1: the proportion of degraded land over total land area. The indicator integrates three spatially explicit sub-indicators: trends in land cover, trends in land productivity and trends in carbon stocks. Land productivity dynamics (LPD) has been the proxy for trends in land productivity and a key component of the SDG indicator 15.3.1 (more than 90% in many countries). Accurate LPD estimation depends on consistent and reliable vegetation indices, such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), assessed over time.

While global LPD datasets derived from coarse-resolution NDVI time series (250 m to 8 km) offer extensive temporal and spatial coverage, their resolution is insufficient to capture the fine-scale land changes that are critical for SIDS and other small, heterogeneous landscapes. High-resolution data, such as that provided by the Landsat program (30 m), are better suited for national- and subnational-scale assessments, but their use is complicated in SIDS due to persistent cloud cover, limited acquisitions during key monitoring periods (Landsat 5 TM mission), and historical data gaps caused by the Landsat 7 Scan Line Corrector (SLC) failure in 2003.

To address these limitations, Apacheta, the Partnership Initiative for Sustainable Land Management (PISLM) and Conservation International have developed a harmonized 30 m NDVI time series for 40 SIDS, covering 2000–2023. This dataset integrates three complementary Landsat-based data streams: (i) all available Landsat 5, 7, 8, and 9 imagery; (ii) 32-day NDVI composites from the United States Geological Survey (USGS); and (iii) synthetic observations generated using the Continuous Change Detection and Classification (CCDC) algorithm. Data fusion techniques, including iterative spatial averaging, temporal interpolation, and outlier suppression, are applied to minimize the impact of persistent cloud cover, limited acquisitions, and SLC-off gaps, resulting in a temporally consistent, spatially complete NDVI record.

This 30 m NDVI time series is designed to provide a robust, harmonized vegetation dataset that supports the derivation of LPD at a resolution and quality suitable for SIDS. The resulting product enables more accurate assessments of land productivity trends, supporting evidence-based decision-making, national SDG 15.3.1 reporting, and the implementation of Land Degradation Neutrality (LDN) strategies in vulnerable island contexts.

Chapter I: 30m NDVI Dataset 2000-2023

A 30 m NDVI time series (2000–2023) was constructed by integrating three complementary Landsat-based datasets. The combined approach leverages the strengths of each source while mitigating their individual limitations, particularly for periods and regions with persistent data gaps. The three input datasets are:

1. LS: A collection made by us with all available Landsat 5, 7, 8, and 9 surface reflectance imagery
2. L32: Landsat 32-Day NDVI Composite by Google/USGS¹ with some filters
3. CCDC Synthetic image: NDVI imagery generated using the Continuous Change Detection and Classification algorithm (CCDC, Arévalo et al. 2020)

These datasets were harmonized into a single time series through a combination of temporal interpolation, spatial gap-filling, and cloud/SLC-off correction.

Why use three datasets to build one time series?

No single time series is free from limitations. Building a robust product requires careful decisions about: Noise handling (clouds, atmospheric effects, striping), Gap filling (persistent cloud cover, SLC-off impacts, limited acquisitions), Annual compositing choices (mean, median, maximum, or other metrics).

Each dataset has specific strengths and weaknesses. By combining them, we aim to maximize coverage, minimize noise, and provide a time series more resilient to the challenging observational conditions typical of SIDS. A more detailed evaluation of the individual datasets is presented in Chapter 2.

Input datasets

LS: Landsat 5-7-8-9

Includes all available Landsat 5 (TM sensor), Landsat 7 (ETM+ sensor), Landsat 8 (OLI sensor), and Landsat 9 (OLI-2 sensor) surface reflectance imagery for the period 2000–2023. The imagery, processed to orthorectified surface reflectance, was filtered to include the blue, green, red, near-infrared (NIR), and shortwave-infrared 1 (SWIR1) bands, along with the “QA_PIXEL” band used for cloud masking. NDVI was calculated for each image following Huang et al. (2021) as the normalized difference between NIR and red bands. An additional cloud mask was applied using the Normalized Difference Snow Index (NDSI; Zhu et al., 2018), computed from the green and SWIR1 bands, with pixels having $NDSI \leq 0.5$ excluded to further reduce cloud contamination.

L32: Landsat 32-Day

The Landsat Collection 2 Tier 1 Level 2 32-Day NDVI Composite (courtesy of the U.S. Geological Survey), available in the Google Earth Engine repository¹. The composite is generated from all cloud-free scenes within each 32-day period, beginning on the first day of the year and continuing through

¹https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog/LANDSAT_COMPOSITES_C02_T1_L2_32DAY_NDVI

day 352. This dataset complements the LS collection by trying to provide temporally regular composites.

CCDC Synthetic images

The third dataset consists of synthetic NDVI imagery generated using the Continuous Change Detection and Classification (CCDC) algorithm (Zhu & Woodcock, 2014). The algorithm fits harmonic functions to the LS NDVI series, estimating model coefficients and identifying breakpoints when significant changes occur. New coefficients are generated for each segment between breakpoints, enabling the estimation of pixel values for any date in the series. Synthetic NDVI images were produced only for locations where LS and L32 data were absent for more than two consecutive years, in order to optimize processing efficiency. Following Arevalo et al. (2020)², four synthetic images per year were generated, restricted to the NIR and red bands, sufficient for NDVI calculation.

Methodology

Progressive spatial filter

Persistent gaps caused by cloud masking, invalid QA_PIXEL flags, or Landsat 7 SLC-off stripes were first addressed within each series (LS and L32) using a size-progressive mean spatial filter. This method fills missing values by progressively expanding the search radius, starting with immediate neighbors (1-pixel radius). If the 1-pixel neighborhood does not provide sufficient data; the search is expanded to a 2-pixel radius, and it keeps going to a maximum of 3 pixels. This approach ensures that the interpolation is always based on the closest possible valid pixels, minimizing spatial smoothing and preserving local NDVI variability, which is particularly important for heterogeneous landscapes in SIDS. These gaps could be very persistent in the final annual median image, specifically in the early 2000's when there less available images per year that could provide data in those pixels. The effect of this procedure on the annual median NDVI can be seen in the Image 1 below.

² <https://github.com/parevalo/gee-ccdc-tools>

Fig. 1: Comparison of annual medians in Saint Lucia 2005 with and without progressive spatial filter.

Annual compositing: Time series collections

Once spatial gaps were reduced, annual median NDVI values were calculated for each series to build an image collection. For L32, the annual median was calculated directly from the spatially filtered 32-day composites available. For LS, monthly medians were calculated first, followed by annual medians, to better represent intra-annual NDVI dynamics.

Filling temporal gaps

Remaining temporal gaps in the Annual collections were addressed using a two-step approach:

- Gaps of one year were filled by averaging the NDVI values from the preceding and subsequent years.
- Gaps longer than one year were filled using CCDC synthetic imagery collection as a predictor.

This was applied separately to LS and L32 before merging (Next step).

Merging LS and L32

Because LS and L32 were constructed independently, small differences in NDVI values for the same pixel and year could occur, often related to cloud contamination or phenological effects. For each pixel-year, the maximum NDVI value between the two series was selected as the best pixel and least cloud-affected value.

Noise removal

The merged time series was then inspected for outliers. In years with very few valid observations, single-year NDVI down-spikes were sometimes evident. To remove these events, the difference between each annual NDVI value and the mean of the preceding and following years was calculated. If this difference exceeded 10% of the moving mean, the value was replaced with that mean.

The complete workflow is summarized in Figure 2, and an example of the resulting time series composition is shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 2: Flowchart of NDVI Gap Filled time series of 30 m.

Fig. 3: Time series construction example. Above chart shows original annual medians. Below chart shows the result of merging TS using max NDVI (green line), CCDC filling gaps (blue line) and noise removing (red line).

Chapter II: Development and Testing of Landsat-Based NDVI Time Series

Chapter 1 described the final process developed for producing the mixed NDVI gap-filled time series from Landsat imagery, optimized for input to the LPD model. That procedure is the outcome of a broader analytical process in which multiple parametrizations, datasets, and filters were tested. These intermediate approaches may still be useful under different conditions or for alternative objectives. In practice, time series models should be explored and adjusted at national or regional levels to better align with the spatial and temporal patterns observed on the ground. This chapter describes in greater detail the procedures applied, along with the alternative configurations tested during the time series construction process.

First generation Landsat time series

The initial step in developing the NDVI time series was to review the available Landsat datasets, assessing both temporal and spatial coverage. This analysis revealed significant gaps in Landsat 5 coverage for many SIDS, particularly in the Caribbean (Figure 6) and Pacific (Figure 7). For the period 2000 to 2013, most islands were covered almost exclusively by Landsat 7. Due to lower acquisition frequency and the Scan Line Corrector (SLC) failure of Landsat 7 in 2003, this period presents reduced temporal density and large gaps due also to cloud effect.

Fig. 6: Landsat 5 (left) and 7 (right) coverage in Caribbean islands for period 2000-2023.

Fig. 7: Landsat 5 (above) and 7 (below) coverage in Pacific islands for period 2000-2023.

in this context, a second dataset was introduced to compensate for these gaps: the Landsat Collection 2 Tier 1 Level 2 32-Day NDVI Composite (L32). While both LS and L32 are derived from the same Landsat observations, the cloud masking methods and compositing processes differ, leading to

distinct coverage patterns. This is evident, for example, in the number of valid observations available per pixel in each dataset (Figure 8).

Fig. 8: Number of available images in 2005 by collection in Saint Lucia.

The first generation of Landsat time series aimed to rely solely on original collections, using only temporal filters to fill gaps, without spatial ones. In that context, two time series were constructed using each dataset by calculating annual NDVI medians. For LS collection monthly medians were obtained previous to the annuals, while for L32 that step was not necessary.

Since the resulting time series contained some no data pixels, a temporal filter was employed for filling those gaps. Then, no data pixels were filled with the average of previous and next year. A significant improvement in the time series resulted from that filter, but there were still many no data pixels, especially in cloudy areas and scan line error affected years. Those remaining no data pixels are due to temporal gaps longer than one year. Then a new temporal filter was added to the first: temporal gaps longer than one year were filled with CCDC synthetic images (Fig. 9). Each step of time series construction and filtering was evaluated not only at the time series level, but also at LPD result (Fig. 10).

First-Generation Construction Approach

The first-generation Landsat NDVI time series aimed to rely entirely on the original datasets, applying only temporal gap-filling filters and no spatial interpolation was used at this stage. Two independent annual NDVI series were constructed: one from LS and one from L32.

- For LS, monthly median NDVI values were first calculated for each year to better capture seasonal variability, followed by annual medians.
- For L32, the annual median NDVI was computed directly from the 32-day composites, as these already integrate intra-annual variation.

Because both time series still contained missing pixels, a temporal filter was applied:

- Single-year gaps were filled using the average NDVI value of the preceding and following years.

This filter produced a substantial improvement in data completeness. However, many gaps remained, particularly in persistently cloudy regions or years heavily affected by Landsat 7 SLC-off striping. The remaining missing pixels were primarily due to temporal gaps longer than one year. To address this, a second temporal filter was introduced:

- Multi-year gaps were filled using synthetic NDVI values generated with the Continuous Change Detection and Classification (CCDC) algorithm.

This allowed for the reconstruction of missing years where observations were unavailable from LS or L32 (Figure 9).

Each step of time series construction and filtering was evaluated not only by exploring the effects on different years, but also on the final product that we aimed to obtain: the LPD maps for different periods (Fig. 10).

Fig. 9: Gap filling process in 2007 LS annual median

Fig. 10: Resulting LPD maps in Saint Lucia using first generation LS time series.

Second generation Mixed Series

The first-generation series and LPD outputs represented a significant improvement over the available 250 m global products. However, some challenges persisted: as shown in Figure 10, residual cloud artefacts, scan line errors, and gaps due to persistent cloud cover were still evident. To address these without introducing additional satellite data, extra processing steps were incorporated into the workflow.

A progressive spatial filter was applied to both LS and L32 collections before annual compositing. Each image was filled locally, beginning with the mean of immediate 1-pixel neighbors. Pixels that remained empty after this step were filled with a second filter at a radius of two pixels, and finally (only when necessary) a radius of three pixels was used (Figure 11). This step substantially reduced the number of empty pixels, particularly those caused by Landsat 7 scan line errors and in highly clouded years.

Fig. 11: NDVI median of year 2007 on a section of Samoa with (left) and without (right) spatial gap filter. Below each image, charts showing original stacks and mixed TS in coordinates Lon.: - 171.67186; Lat.: -13.93190.

Once spatial filtering was applied to each image, annual median NDVI values were calculated in the same way as for the first-generation series: monthly medians followed by annual medians for LS, and direct annual medians for L32.

Each annual time series was then corrected for single-year temporal gaps using the average of the preceding and following years. At this point, both series were generally complete, but minor differences between them persisted due to cloud contamination, acquisition dates, or filtering effects. To minimize these discrepancies, the two series were merged by selecting the maximum NDVI value for each pixel-year, based on the assumption that the higher value is less affected by cloud contamination.

Remaining gaps longer than one year were filled with CCDC synthetic images, applied selectively where neither LS nor L32 provided valid data.

Finally, a one-year drop correction was applied to all pixels where the NDVI value for a given year differed by more than 10% from the mean of the preceding and following years. This correction helped eliminate isolated extreme values caused by scarce acquisitions or persistent cloud cover, thereby reducing noise in the final time series.

In the specific example of Saint Lucia we can observe the percentage of pixels that come from the different sections of the algorithm and time series (Figure 12) in each year. Most years have 85% or more of their pixels coming directly from LS or L32 Time series with no time interpolation needed.

Fig. 12: Source of each NDVI pixel in Saint Lucia on each year.

The process was iteratively executed for 40 SIDS in Google Earth Engine, producing a list of Assets that can be seen in Annex 1. Also, by using the new FAO-WOCAT³ version 2 algorithm with a default parametrization of “Priority Mode” a first set of LPD maps for all 40 SIDS and the 3 periods of 2026 UNCCD Reporting Process was built (see Fig. 13 and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15276519>).

Fig. 13: Resulting LPD maps in Saint Lucia using second generation LS time series.

³ FAO-WOCAT version2 (FWv2 - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10849367>)

Chapter IV: Exploring datasets and algorithms

To facilitate the exploration and evaluation of the constructed NDVI time series, a dedicated web application ([30m NDVI Time Series explorer](#)) was developed. This tool is designed to support interactive inspection of the datasets, enabling detailed analysis of temporal patterns and the impact of the applied processing steps.

The NDVI Time Series Explorer allows users to select any of the 40 SIDS and load the corresponding outputs: LPD maps + Annual NDVI time series, available with or without the spatial gap filter applied

By interacting directly with the map, users can examine local NDVI dynamics in detail. Clicking on any location generates three charts:

1.- Original LS and L32 NDVI stacks

The first chart displays the annual median NDVI values from the LS and L32 series separately, showing how each dataset captures vegetation dynamics over time (Figure 14).

2.- Composition of the mixed time series

The second chart illustrates how the final mixed NDVI series is constructed:

- The green thick line represents the maximum NDVI value between the LS and L32 annual series, chosen as the least cloud-affected value.
- The blue thick line indicates NDVI values filled with CCDC synthetic imagery, applied for temporal gaps longer than one year.
- The red thin line shows the resulting corrected series, after applying the one-year drop correction.

3.- Number of images used per year

The third chart displays the number of valid images available for each year's median NDVI calculation (Figure 15), providing context for interpreting potential anomalies or variations in the series.

This interactive visualization tool supports both dataset quality assessment and algorithm evaluation, offering transparency on the construction of the NDVI series and the role of each processing step.

Fig. 14: Overview of NDVI time series and LPD maps explorer app.

Fig. 15: Screenshot of charts deployed in NDVI time series and LPD maps explorer app.

References:

Arévalo, P., Bullock, E.L., Woodcock, C.E., Olofsson, P. (2020). A suite of tools for Continuous Land Change Monitoring in Google Earth Engine. *Frontiers in Climate*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fclim.2020.576740>

Huang, S., Tang, L., Hupy, J. P., Wang, G., & Zhao, C. (2021). A commentary review on the use of normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) in the era of popular remote sensing. *Journal of Forestry Research*, 32(1), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11676-020-01155-1>

Zhu, Z., & Woodcock, C. E. (2014). Continuous change detection and classification of land cover using all available Landsat data. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 144, 152–171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2014.01.011>

Zhu, Z., Qiu, S., He, B., & Deng, C. (2018). Cloud and cloud shadow detection for Landsat images: The fundamental basis for analyzing Landsat time series. In Q. Weng (Ed.), *Remote sensing time series image processing* (pp. 3–23). CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781315166636>

Annex 1: List of Asses containing the 30 Mixed Landsat Image Time Series

The following GEE script can be used to extract the Asset Name and explore the data:

<https://code.earthengine.google.com/3b84f3360e8e84d75c60f479b4d16bab>

License: All the datasets are provided with a **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License**. <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Names can also be found here:

```
var Antigua_and_Barbuda = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Antigua_and_Barbuda_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Bahamas = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Bahamas_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
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var Belize = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Belize_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
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var Cook_Islands = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Cook_Islands_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
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var Dominican_Republic = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Dominican_Republic_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
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var Kiribati = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Kiribati_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
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var Nauru = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Nauru_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Niue = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Niue_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Palau = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Palau_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Papua_New_Guinea = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Papua_New_Guinea_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
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var Saint_Lucia = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Saint_Lucia_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Saint_Vincent_and_the_Grenadines = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Saint_Vincent_and_the_Grenadines_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Samoa = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Samoa_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Sao_Tome_and_Principe = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Sao_Tome_and_Principe_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Seychelles = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Seychelles_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Singapore = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Singapore_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Solomon_Islands = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Solomon_Islands_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Suriname = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Suriname_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Timor_Leste = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Timor-Leste_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Tonga = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Tonga_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Trinidad_and_Tobago = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Trinidad_and_Tobago_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Tuvalu = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Tuvalu_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Vanuatu = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Vanuatu_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
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